

Keeping people safe with real-time flood forecasting at Ratnapura

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Abstract: Floods are devastating natural disasters worldwide - it's estimated that every year, 250 million people around the world are affected by floods, also costing billions of dollars in damages. Around Sri Lanka, floods cause over a hundred fatalities every year. 20 percent of those are in Ratnapura district and between 150 Million and 300 Million Rupee in economic damages. Reliable early warning systems have been shown to prevent a significant fraction of fatalities and economic damage, but many people don't have access to those types of warning systems. Flood forecasting can help individuals and authorities better prepare to keep people safe, but accurate forecasting isn't available in Sri Lanka and the warning systems that do exist can be imprecise and non-actionable, resulting in far too many people being underprepared and underinformed before a flood happens.

Key Words: Flood Forecasting, Disaster, Early Warning

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Sri Lanka is highly Sensitive Island for natural disasters. It is located in the Indian Ocean therefore sudden climatic changes occur. Research on climatic changes and its patterns around Sri Lanka will be useful to realize the natural disasters like flood and landslide which are more common and frequent. Minor floods occur every year in between May to December. A major flood has occurred in Kalu Ganga basin in the year, 2003 and 2017 recently. The major flood has damaged lives, assets, cultivations, and infrastructure causing subsequent impact on sanitary problems, diseases, resettlement issues. Western, Southern and Sabaragamuwa provinces are constantly affected by the flood. Ratnapura district frequently faces the challenges of flood hazards from May to September every year. The South-West monsoon arrives with carrying 2000mm of rainwater (50% of total annual rainfall) and the inter-monsoon period from October to November carrying 1000mm of rainwater (22% of total annual rainfall). Although annual rainfall of 4000mm affects to Ratnapura, above two periods are the heavy rainy seasons that caused for flooding. It aggravates when there is a low

pressure created in Bengal bay of Indian Ocean. Kalu River is originating from Adam's Peak at an elevation over 2250m above mean sea level (MSL). It flows through Ratnapura town, which located in a comparatively lowland at about 18m to 305m (MSL) and several tributaries are joined in between. It flows through Ratnapura towards the sea at Kaluthara. Ratnapura low lying riverine area is inundated in peak rainy season.

According to historical data, more than 300mm rainfall within 24 hours at upper catchment sometimes caused a major flood at the urbanized area. There are not any flood controlling or warning systems in the current situation. There are new techniques practicing in Japan to mitigate and control the flood. For example, Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) disseminates warning and information about disaster via various channels in order to reach people surely and quickly, for example, JMA has given an emergency warning during the Typhoon Man-Yi in 2013. Sri Lanka can adapt those technics to mitigate the disaster risk reduction program.

1.1 Background:

Kalu Ganga is the third longest river (110 km) in Sri Lanka originating from Adam's peak at an elevation over 2000m above Mean Sea Level (MSL) discharging 4000MCM annually to the sea. It flows through Ratnapura town, which situated in a comparatively low land at about 18 m (MSL), where flooding is a common phenomenon whenever there is heavy rainfall over the peak range (upstream catchment). Several tributaries covering a catchment area of 603 km² contribute to Kalu Ganga in its' section through Malwala to Ratnapura while Wey Ganga River through Kahawatta area joins Kalu Ganga at Ratnapura town adding a higher flood risk to the main town. The inadequacy of river gradient of 0.15 m/km downstream from Ratnapura town to Kaluthara to convey the excess water surging to the town from both rivers during heavy rains increases the risk of town being flooded frequently. Regular monsoon rains cause minor floods and landslide in low lying areas of Ratnapura, while occasional torrential rains caused by cyclonic storms originating in the Bay of Bengal in a frequency of once in about a decade cause major floods in both the Ratnapura and Kalutara districts. There are High Flood Level's (HFL) marked on historical buildings around the city area in Ratnapura. Maximum recorded flood was in 1947 flood, but more damages were occurred in 2003, 18th May flood.

Damage Report of 2017 May 26th Flood (Flood and Landslide) - Ratnapura District	
Affected Numbers of Divisional Sectararian	17
Affected Numbers of Grama Niladari Division	423
Affected Numbers of Families	60,080
Affected Numbers of Members	235,197
Numbers of Refugee Centers	221
Refugee of Families	11,865
Refugee of Members	47,064
Numbers of Deaths	86
Numbers of Missing	15
House Damages	
Full	721
Half	10,944
Damage of House - hold Goods and Equipment	12,556
Numbers of Resettlement Families	
Families at Land slide Areas	229
Families at Land slide Prone Areas	1,290
Families at Flood Prone Areas	212
Cost need for Reconstruction of Infrastructures	Rs. 15,254,000.62

2.0 RATIONALE

Flood threats in Ratnapura town have caused many deaths and millions of rupees damages to properties and infrastructure. Such major floods were occurred in the recent past in 1992, 2003 and 2017. In the year 2003, 18th May flood caused 122 deaths and had affected 34,000 families. Destruction created by it also costs over one thousand million rupees including houses, schools, public buildings, roadways, irrigation schemes, and industries. Even though the climate and geometry of river cannot be changed or controlled, the human activities in the upper catchment can be controlled and changes to catchment surface and early warning system may be a remedy for above unbalance environmental situation.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

To help improve awareness of impending floods, first, we plan to use real-time measurements of precipitation and river water levels to create better forecasting models that will predict when floods occur and incorporating that information into public alerts. A variety of elements-from historical events to river level readings, to the terrain and elevation of a specific area-feed into our computers. Second, we can generate high-resolution elevation maps and run up to hundreds of thousands of simulations in each location. Third, we plan to collect information through our partners (For example, Irrigation Department, Metrology Department, and NBRO) and we hope to create river flood, forecasting models. From there, we will generate alerts. Finally, with this information, we can create river flood forecasting alerts that can more accurately predict not only when and where a flood might occur, but also the severity of the event.

Here's more on the progress we've made over this year. This year we began our initiative in the Muwagama region of Ratnapura, with the goal of providing

accurate real-time flood forecasting information and alerts to those in affected regions. We make this possible through real-time information which incorporates data from historical flooding events, river levels, terrain, and elevation data. We plan to expand our coverage area next year. Now we are covering 300 sq. kilometers in Ratnapura along the Kalu River, one of the most flood-affected river in Sri Lanka. We've also sent over 500 alerts to individuals in affected areas.

The alerts we send out include four tiers of risk: Alert Flood Level, Minor Flood Level, Major Flood Level, and Critical Flood Level. Accuracy and reliability are paramount to the success of the initiative, and the safety of those in affected areas. Incorrect forecasts do more harm than good, and vague or overly general warnings are consistently ignored by affected populations. We track the accuracy of our alerts across manual measurements. Automated SMS alerts will send to pre-defined authorities each identified water levels.

3.1 The Early Warning System

Message 01: Alert Flood Level (5.2m, Reduce Level of Mumagama river gauge)

Alert Flood Level is the level at which river water has risen to a sufficient level to start warning to the community. The rate of water level rising is further increasing means that people should be warned and authorities should get ready for any situation. If the rate of water level rising is getting low, indicates to observe precipitation over the catchment area for the next couple of hours.

Message 02: Minor Flood Level (7.5m, Reduce Level of Mumagama river gauge)

Minor Flood Level indicates that river water has risen adequately to cause inundation of areas that are not normally covered by water. For example, village roads will inundate. Recently, in the year 2019, 18th

Figure 1 -The Early Warning System

of July, Muwagama gauge reached a minor flood level. Information about affected houses and GNs divisions collected by the DMC office. The rate of rising this water level further increase indicates to observe rain-fall over the catchment and it leads to be flood vast majority of forecasted area in the next couple of hours.

Message 03: Major Flood Level (9.5m, Reduce Level of Mumagama river gauge)

This tells us a huge percentage of land ended up being flooded. Recently, in year 2018, 21st of May, Muwagama gauge reached 9.00m and information about affected houses and GNs divisions collected by Ratnapura DMC office. Rate of rising water level further increase means people must vacate to safe locations.

Message 04: Critical Flood Level (10.5m, Reduce Level of Mumagama river gauge)

This illustrates the magnitude of the flood disaster. Authorities can use flood maps developed by the irrigation department for rescue operations. Recently, in the year 2017, 26th of May, Muwagama gauge read 11.63m. On that day, all A, B and C class roads from Colombo to Pelmadulla nundated by flood.

3.2 Distributing Alerts

Accurate and reliable flood forecasting can help keep people safe if they're getting the early warning. Over the past year, we've significantly improved our notification infrastructure. We've expanded the early warning we used to inform affected individuals, by adding better crisis information on social media. Whether they find out about the flooding event through Search, Maps, or an alert push notification, people can quickly access a web base flood map where they can see their location relative to where the flood is predicted to be.

To enable even faster progress in the future, we've increased the efficiency of our simulation models, automating manual tasks, and experimenting with new forecast methodologies.

3.3 Key partnerships in local communities

Many people don't have access to the internet, especially during a crisis, so we've partnered with the Sri Lankan nonprofit organization (Oxfam) to provide information to individuals on the ground. They send SMS with our real-time forecasting information, and they directly interact with the community and local village councils. This year we've piloted this system in Ratnapura, sending alerts to local leaders across hundreds of villages in the district, and we're actively collecting feedback about how well the system worked.

Our most important partner is the government itself, which not only provides us with critical real-time data, but is also the best-placed to provide relief efforts in times of crises. In the past year, we've developed a partner notification infrastructure to provide our forecasts for the Irrigation Department and other organizational partners (DMC), and are continuously working with them to improve this system to be more effective for disaster management efforts.

Flood management is an enormous challenge, and reducing the immense harms of floods locally will require collaboration between local governments, line organizations, the academic community, and operational experts. By continuing this work, we hope to help develop tools to make forecasts and response systems more accurate and accessible to everyone.

Figure 2 - Dashboard of Mobile App

4.0 REFERENCES

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